

^1H and ^{13}C spectral studies of α,β -unsaturated sulfones

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^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra have been recorded for 1-arylsulfonyl-2-*p*-nitrophenylethylenes **3** (aryl = 2-hydroxy-5-chlorophenyl) and **4** (aryl = 2-hydroxy-5-methylphenyl). The observed coupling constants of ethylenic protons indicate that **3** and **4** exist in *E*-configuration. The chemical shifts of ethylenic α -protons are found to be influenced by the nature of the substituents in the benzene ring attached to sulfonyl group. It is also found that C(α) carbon absorbs downfield in **3** compared to **4** and this can be explained based on different conformations of aryl ring in the compounds.

NMR studies on chalcones reveal that the chemical shifts of ethylenic protons are more sensitive to the effect of substituents in the benzene ring¹⁻³. The study of α,β -unsaturated sulfones which are analogous to chalcones is interesting⁴⁻⁹ since there are contradictory reports concerning the ability of sulfonyl group to conjugate with unsaturated groups directly linked to the sulfonyl group. The existence of conjugative interaction of ethenyl and sulfonyl group in the excited state is proved from the UV spectral studies⁴. However, dipole moment studies⁵ reveal absence of conjugative interaction between sulfonyl group and ethenyl group in the ground state. From the ^1H NMR spectral studies of 2-aryl-1-phenylsulfonylethylenes **1** ($\text{PhSO}_2\text{CH}=\text{CH}-\text{Ar}$) and 1-arylsulfonyl-2-phenylethylenes **2** ($\text{ArSO}_2\text{CH}=\text{CHPh}$). Srinivasan *et al.*⁶ concluded that the chemical shifts of α -protons in **1** (α with respect to sulfonyl group) and β -protons in **2** are more sensitive to the effects of substituents in the benzene ring. Moreover, they have reported the presence of conjugative interaction from the observation of greater contribution of the resonance effect to the chemical shift of β -protons over the field effect in these systems. ^{13}C spectral studies⁷ of **1** and **2** also reveal that the resonance effect is the dominant factor at C- α in series **1** and C- β in series **2**, whereas the inductive effect is predominant at C- β in series **1** with a reverse substituent effect at this carbon atom. Recently the conformations of *cis*- and *trans*-4-bromophenyl styryl sulfone were also analysed in detail by molecular models and by single crystal X-ray diffraction studies⁸. So far no attempt has been made to study the effect of *ortho*-substituents in the benzene ring attached to sulfonyl group on the chemical shifts of ethylenic protons and ethylenic carbons in α,β -unsaturated sulfones. We report here a detailed ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectral study of 1-arylsulfonyl-2-*p*-nitrophenylethylenes [$\text{ArSO}_2\text{CH}=\text{CH}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-(\text{NO}_2-p)$], **3** (Ar = 2-hydroxy-5-chlorophenyl) and **4** (Ar = 2-hydroxy-5-methylphenyl).

Results and Discussion

The signals for all the protons appeared as doublets except for H(6) which appeared as singlet. The assignments of

the signals were done based on coupling constants, integrals and comparison with known compounds. The ethylenic protons H(α) and H(β) can easily be distinguished from the other ring protons based on coupling constants. Among the ethylenic proton signals the upfield one has been assigned to H(α). The protons H(3') and H(5') are expected to absorb at a downfield position relative to other ring protons due to the electron-withdrawing nature of the nitro group in the ring. The most upfield signal should be assigned to the proton *ortho* to hydroxyl group. The signal for H(4) can be easily distinguished from those of H(2') or H(6') based on integration. The ^1H chemical shifts of **3** and **4** are reported in Table 1.

Table 1. ^1H NMR spectral data of **3** and **4**

Compd. no.	H(α) (<i>J</i> , Hz)	H(β) (<i>J</i> , Hz)	H(3') H(5')	H(2') H(6')	H(3)	H(4)	H(6)	Others
3	7.60 (15.48)	7.74 -7.80 (15.48)	8.26	7.74 -7.80	7.06	8.06	8.06	11.5 (OH)
4	7.04 (15.47)	7.69 (15.47)	8.27	7.67	6.95	7.35	7.46	8.66 (OH) 2.32 (CH ₃)

The assignment of the signals in the ^{13}C spectra were made based on intensities, SEFT spectral studies and comparison with known compounds. Among the quaternary carbon signals the hydroxyl bearing carbon is expected to resonate most downfield compared to other quaternary carbons. The next downfield quaternary carbon signal should be assigned to the carbon bearing the nitro group. Due to shielding *ortho* and *para* effect of hydroxyl group the SO_2 bearing quaternary carbon and C-5 are expected to absorb upfield relative to C(1') (*para* carbon with respect to NO_2 group). The signal of the SO_2 bearing carbon is distinguished from the C(5) signal based on the fact that in **3** and **4** it is expected to occur around the same field because the

carbon is *meta* with respect to the C-5 substituent. Among the remaining signals the downfield signal around 140 ppm and the upfield signal around 119 ppm are assigned to C(α) and C(3), respectively, based on known deshielding α -effect of SO₂ group and shielding *ortho*-effect of OH group. The assignments of the remaining signals were done based on comparison with the signals in the appropriate chalcone² and aryl phenyl sulfones¹⁰. Table 2 reports the ¹³C chemical shifts of **3** and **4**.

Table 2. ¹³C NMR spectral data of **3** and **4**

Compd. no.	C(α)	C(β)	C(1)	C(2)	C(3)	C(4)	C(5)	C(6)	Others
			C(1')	C(2')	C(3')	C(4')	C(5')	C(6')	
3	140.67	131.21	126.96	155.27	119.54	135.3	122.64	129.99	
			138.90	127.69	123.98	148.43	123.98	127.69	
4	138.97	131.11	126.97	154.07	119.05	137.76	130.74	129.36	20.25
			138.06	128.56	124.23	149.10	124.23	128.56	

The observed coupling constants of ethylenic protons (≈ 15 Hz) indicate that **3** and **4** exist in *E*-configuration. Comparison of the chemical shifts of ethyl methyl ketone with those of ethyl methyl sulfone reveals that replacement of carbonyl group by sulfonyl group deshields α and β protons by 0.5 and 0.42 ppm, respectively¹¹. Similar comparison of chemical shifts in -CO-CH=CH₂ and -SO₂-CH=CH₂ reveals that replacement of CO group by sulfonyl group deshields α -proton by 0.48 ppm and *trans*- β -proton by 0.14 ppm, but has negligible effect on *cis*- β -protons¹². However, comparison of chemical shifts in C₆H₅-CO-CH=CH-C₆H₅¹ and C₆H₅-SO₂CH=CH-C₆H₅⁶ reveals an opposite trend in ethylenic α -proton chemical shift, i.e. replacement of CO group by SO₂ group shields α -proton by 0.61 ppm. Similar shielding of α -proton by the replacement of carbonyl group by SO₂ group⁶ has been observed in substituted phenyl derivatives also such as C₆H₅-SO₂-CH=CH-C₆H₄-(NO₂-*p*) and (*p*-CH₃O)-C₆H₄-SO₂-CH=CH-C₆H₅.

In the present compounds also similar upfield shift has been noted due to the replacement of CO group by SO₂ group. For example, comparison of the α -proton chemical shifts in chalcone **5** [1-aryl-3-phenyl-2-propene-1-one (aryl = 2-hydroxy-3,5-dimethylphenyl)] with that in **4** reveals that ethylenic α -proton resonates considerably upfield in **4** (δ 7.09) relative to **5** (δ 7.89)¹³. The upfield shifts observed on α -protons in the above cases are attributed to the magnetic anisotropic effect of the phenyl ring attached to SO₂ group. The α -protons are oriented in such a way that they lie probably in the shielding region of the aromatic ring. There is no appreciable change in the chemical shifts of ethylenic β -protons by the replacement of carbonyl group by SO₂ group.

The chemical shifts of **3** and **4** have been compared with the chemical shifts of C₆H₅SO₂CH=CH-C₆H₄-(NO₂-*p*). Such a comparison reveals that introduction of substituents in the benzene ring attached to SO₂ group causes

slight upfield shift on both the ethylenic protons except the α -proton in the chloro compound **3** where considerable downfield shift (+0.50 ppm) has been observed. In other words, replacement of methyl group by chloro group causes the α -proton to resonate considerably downfield (δ 7.60 vs 7.04). The abnormal downfield shift is not due to the electronegativity or inductive effect of chlorine group since α -protons in (*p*-CH₃)-C₆H₄-SO₂-CH=CH-C₆H₅ and (*p*-Cl)-C₆H₄-SO₂CH=CH-C₆H₅ resonate almost around the same field (6.90, 6.88 ppm)⁶. Probably the conformations of the aryl ring attached to SO₂ group in **3** and **4** are different.

It has been previously observed¹⁰ that in *ortho*-substituted diphenyl sulfones, the sulfur atom is approximately tetrahedral and C(1)-S-C(1') plane lies almost perpendicular to the planes of the two aryl rings. In *trans*-4-bromophenyl styryl sulfone, conformations as shown in Fig. 1 were proposed by Srinivasan *et al.*⁸. In conformation **A** the proton H(α) lies on the same side of the aryl ring attached to SO₂ group whereas in conformation **B** it lies on the opposite side. One can expect similar kind of conformations for **3** and **4** also. In the present study, the conformation **B** is however ruled out since in this conformation there will be severe steric interaction between the ethylene moiety and the aromatic ring.

Fig. 1

The conformations approximating **A** are considered in the present study. In the conformation where the phenyl ring at sulfur lies in the plane defined by C(α)-S-C(1) (i.e. Ph-C(α)-C(β) is coplanar with the phenyl ring at sulfur), the proton H(α) experiences severe steric interaction with the *ortho*-proton or substituent of the aryl ring at sulfur. Therefore, the planar conformation is ruled out in the present study for both **3** and **4**. The phenyl rings at sulfur in **3** and **4** are tilted to avoid this steric interaction. In the slightly tilted conformation, the aryl ring at sulfur may be nearly coplanar with the plane containing either of the S=O units. In this conformation H(α) lies in the deshielding zone of the aromatic ring attached to sulfur. If the aryl ring attached to sulfur is tilted to a greater extent then a perpendicular conformation may be obtained. In this conformation, the aryl ring at sulfur lies almost perpendicular to the plane containing C(α)-S-C(1) and H(α) lies in the shielding region of the aryl ring attached to sulfur.

In the methyl compound **4**, the larger size of the substituent and shorter C-C bond distance combined to exert a buttressing effect on H-6 and the resulting interaction with H(α) forces the aromatic ring to tilt to a greater extent, i.e. the methyl compound **4** adopts perpendicular conformation. However, in the chloro compound **3** the interaction is less and hence it adopts the slightly tilted conformation. In the perpendicular conformation of the methyl compound **4** the proton H(α) lies in the shielding region of the aryl ring. However, in the less tilted conformation of the chloro compound **3**, the proton H(α) experiences deshielding due to magnetic anisotropic effect of the aryl ring at sulfur. Thus, the different conformations of the aryl ring at sulfur are responsible for the upfield resonance of H(α) in **4** relative to **3**.

The hydroxyl proton absorbs considerably downfield in the chloro compound **3** (11.5 ppm) relative to the methyl compound **4** (8.66 ppm). In the less tilted conformation of the chloro compound **3** hydrogen bonding is possible to both the S=O groups. However, in the perpendicular conformation of the methyl compound **4** (the aryl ring at sulfur is coplanar with the other S=O unit) the hydrogen bonding is possible to only one S=O unit. This is probably the reason for the downfield resonance of hydroxyl proton in **3** compared to **4**.

It is seen from Table 2 that the ethylenic α -carbon resonates considerably downfield in the chloro compound **3** (140.7 ppm) compared to methyl compound **4** (139.0 ppm). In **4** the deshielding influence of SO₂ group is expected to be less since the aryl ring attached to SO₂ group is perpendicular to the C(1)-S-C(α) plane. However, in **3** the aryl ring is only slightly tilted and hence deshielding influence is more. This is probably the reason for the downfield resonance of C(α) carbon in **3** relative to **4**.

Experimental

The α,β -unsaturated sulfones **3** and **4** were prepared by literature methods¹⁴ and their purity was checked by TLC : **3** (Found : C, 49.85; H, 2.93; N, 4.0. C₁₄H₁₀SO₅NCl calcd. for : C, 49.49; H, 2.95; N, 4.1%); **4** (Found : C, 56.56; H, 4.04; N, 4.44. C₁₅H₁₃SO₅N calcd. for : C, 56.35; H, 4.07; N,

4.38%). ^1H NMR spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrometer (200 MHz) using TMS as internal standard and ^{13}C NMR spectra (CDCl₃) at 50 MHz. To assist the assignment of signals SEFT spectra were also recorded.

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